

Project Acronym: Q-SORT
Grant Agreement number: 766970
Project Title: Q-SORT. The Quantum Sorter: A New Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy

Interdisciplinary Training Webinar (release 5) D3.9

Version 1.0

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Project funded by the European Commission within the FET OPEN Programme		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	19/08/2019	Raffaella Santucci Luca Marco Carlo Giberti	QED QED	Outline of the document
0.2	23/08/2019	Raffaella Santucci	QED	First draft
0.3	03/09/2019	Gerd Leuchs	MPI	Comments
0.4	15/09/2019	Vincenzo Grillo Raffaella Santucci	CNR QED	First complete version
0.4.9	19/09/2019	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti	QED	Second complete version - overall cleanup
0.5	28/09/2019	Enzo Rotunno, Amir H. Tavabi	CNR FZJ	Review and comments
1.0	30/09/2019	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti Raffaella Santucci	QED QED	Final version integrating the comments of the peer reviewers and partners

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the “*Shaping electron wavepackets with light; Shaping light with electron wavepackets*” webinar. This is the fourth in the planned series of 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars for the Q-SORT project.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars are part of Work Package 3 **Theory, optical testing, and TEM implementation of generalised Sorter** [Months: 1-41], Task 3.5 - Interdisciplinary Training Webinars (M6, M11, M12, M18, M24, M26, M30, M36, M41).

This document is comprised of four Chapters, including Introduction and Conclusions.

The Introduction describes what a webinar is.

Chapter 2 summarises what we mean by Interdisciplinary Training Webinars and what their function is within Q-SORT.

Chapter 3 illustrates context, aims, and content of the fourth Interdisciplinary Training Webinar of Q-SORT. The conclusions outline future plans for the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHAT IS A WEBINAR?

A webinar is a web-based seminar which can be streamed either live or on demand. It might be just a simple audio stream, or it might include visual aids, such as PowerPoint slides, recorded video clips, or live software demonstrations.

The experience of a webinar attempts to reproduce the benefits of attending a seminar. Audience members can ask questions and the speaker can survey or poll the audience and get feedback as he or she delivers the information.

Webinar technology providers need to support these interactive elements in addition to the basic delivery of the audio and video streams. Keyboard chat features and Q&A are usually subject to more control, whereby the presenters can see messages from the audience and choose whether to broadcast them to all participants, ignore them, or reply privately.

The Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Webinars make use of Facebook Live as a platform for live streaming. We chose this platform as it provides the best value for money and offers the added advantage of being very widespread. Users are able to pose questions by posting comments below the video. Answers can be provided by specialists during or after the webinar.

2 THE Q-SORT INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINARS

The Q-SORT project is intrinsically interdisciplinary, being born from the cross-fertilisation of three subject areas: light optics (UG, MPI), electron microscopy (CNR, FZJ, UMR, FEI), and biology (MU).

The silo-breaking nature of Q-SORT provides added value through the following cross-fertilisation dynamics: microscopists borrow techniques from light optics specialists and in turn explain the challenges of the new measurements; biologists explain to physicists the problems that usually arise when studying proteins and suggest alternative proteins for investigation; physicists develop the quantum mechanical approach to cryo-TEM; biologists communicate a priori knowledge to light optics theoreticians in order to streamline efforts in the project work-packages (WP3-WP5).

In order to facilitate mutual learning between physicists and biologists, as well as to foster possible further applications to biology and the life sciences, 9 Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinars have been planned during the lifetime of the project. Their main aim is to function as aids to facilitate the highly interdisciplinary work in WP3 and in the other research WPs. They will do so by providing opportunities for training and mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, for forging a common language, for exchanging ideas for further joint research.

However important their role within Q-SORT, these seminars are meant to be accessible to everyone, hence the choice to propose them as webinars, so as to reach as wide an audience as possible.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars introduce a sort of 'intermediate level' in the communication of science: i.e. their nature is intermediate between the specialist-to-specialist character of discipline-specific communication tools -such as colloquia, talks, papers- and the broad appeal of conventional public understanding of science.

This is why, besides their facilitating function within WP3 and the other research WPs, the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process. Together with the Website, they ensure that Q-SORT will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

In the following paragraph we describe the fifth of the 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars planned for Q-SORT.

3 THE Q-SORT FIFTH INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR:

DESIGN AND POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS OF PATTERNED ELECTRON MIRRORS

Pieter Kruit, Delft University of Technology (The Netherlands)

02 July 2019 h. 3:00- 4:00 PM CET

[Facebook Live: https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/](https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/)

[Q-SORT Website: http://www.qsort.eu/interdisciplinary-training-webinar-5/site](http://www.qsort.eu/interdisciplinary-training-webinar-5/site)

The “*Shaping electron wavepackets with light; Shaping light with electron wavepackets*” *Interdisciplinary Training Webinar* was recorded and webcast on 02 July 2018, during the second [International Conference on Quantum Imaging and Beam Shaping](#) at Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light. The conference was organised by Q-SORT and the “[Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms](#)” DIP project (*Deutsch-Israelische Projekt cooperation grant*) with the support of the Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light and the [Nanoscience Institute of CNR \(CNR-NANO\)](#).

The webinar featured one of conference invited speakers, **Pieter Kruit, Delft University of Technology (The Netherlands)**

Pieter Kruit’s webinar totaled 36K views and 82 reactions (like, love, etc.). Facebook posts related to this webinar reached over 100K people.

The webinar was recorded with two cameras -one for the speaker, the other for the screen and the laser pointer-, then stored on remote servers for subsequent on-demand viewing.

The content of the Webinar was agreed upon by the Project Coordinator, Dr. Vincenzo Grillo (CNR) with Prof. Pieter Kruit (Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands) and Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED).

The webinar can be re-watched on demand - interested parties can re-play it at their convenience by clicking on the following links:

on the Q-SORT website:

<http://www.qsort.eu/interdisciplinary-training-webinar-5/>

on Facebook:

<https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/videos/2295415523827400/>

3.1 TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION

The fifth Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar touches upon the following topics:

- Electron mirrors;

- Programmable phase plates;
- Interaction free microscopy.

Following a recent suggestion [1] that interaction-free measurements [2] are possible with electrons, we have analysed the possibilities available to use this concept for imaging biological specimens with reduced damage. We have also made preliminary designs for an atomic-resolution interaction-free electron microscope, or “quantum electron microscope” [3]. In such a microscope, two novel elements are needed: a double mirror, which enables an electron to pass multiple times through the same region, and a splitter/coupler, which splits an electron wave front in two parts or combines two parts back into one. The role of the splitter should be equivalent to that of a semitransparent mirror in relation to light. We found that the mirror can be combined with the coupler in a grating mirror [4]. By having the electron wavefront reflect on an equipotential surface with a line pattern, the reflected electron picks up a phase modulation which develops in the far field into a diffraction pattern. Of course, we are not restricted to a line pattern on the mirror, so, with a few notable restrictions, it is possible to imprint an arbitrary phase pattern onto an electron wave. This may be an alternative for a programmable phase plate in transmission mode [5].

References

- 1] Putnam, W.; Yanik, M. Phys. Rev. A 2009, 80, 040902.
- 2] Elitzur, A. C.; Vaidman, L. Found. Phys. 1993, 23, 987–997.
- 3] Kruit, P.; Hobbs, R. G.; et al, Ultramicroscopy (2016), doi:10.1016/j.ultramic.2016.03.004.
- 4] M.A.R. Krielaart and P. Kruit, Physical Review A 98 (2018), p. 063806.
- 5] J. Verbeeck et al, Ultramicroscopy 190 (2018), p. 58-65.

3.2 THE FIFTH INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR ON THE Q-SORT WEBSITE

A dedicated webpage for this webinar has been created on the Q-SORT website featuring:

1. the webinar;
2. a short description of the webinar thought for the general public;
3. a short bio of the speaker who offered the talk.

The link to the webpage is:

<http://www.qsort.eu/interdisciplinary-training-webinar-5/>

An overview and a screenshot of the webpage are provided below.

Design and potential applications of patterned electron mirrors

Pieter Kruit, Delft University of Technology (The Netherlands)

02 July 2019 h. 3:00- 4:00 PM CET

[Facebook Live: https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/](https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/)

The sixth Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar touches upon the following topics:

- Electron mirrors;
- Programmable phase plates;
- Interaction free microscopy.

Following a recent suggestion [1] that interaction-free measurements [2] are possible with electrons, we have analyzed the possibilities to use this concept for imaging of biological specimen with reduced damage. We have also made preliminary designs for an atomic resolution interaction-free electron microscope, or “quantum electron microscope” [3]. In such a microscope we need two novel elements: a double mirror which enables an electron to pass multiple times through the same region, and a splitter/coupler which splits an electron wave front in two parts or combines two parts back into one. The latter should be equivalent to what a semitransparent mirror can do for light. We found that the mirror can be combined with the coupler in a grating mirror [4]. By having the electron wave front reflect on an equipotential surface with a line pattern, the reflected electron picks up a phase modulation which develops in the far field into a diffraction pattern. Of course, we are not restricted to a line pattern on the mirror, so, with a few notable restrictions, it is possible to imprint an arbitrary phase pattern onto an electron wave. This may be an alternative for a programmable phase plate in transmission mode [5].

About the speaker

Pieter Kruit is full professor of physics at Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands. He has held a chair in charged particle optics since 1989. He is the (co)author of over 200 publications, the author of 50 international patents, and the supervisor of 35 PhDs. His research is related to the development of electron- and ion-optical instruments for microscopy or nano-lithography. His innovative designs often use MEMS structures. He is presently applying this technology in designs for a Quantum Electron Microscope where the non-demolition principles are investigated for application in low dose microscopy. Most of his work is performed in cooperation with industry. Based on his work he founded, with his graduates, the companies MAPPER Lithography and DELMIC. Among his organizational responsibilities was the editorship of Ultramicroscopy.

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the fourth interdisciplinary training webinar page on the Q-SORT website

4 CONCLUSIONS

This is the fifth Interdisciplinary Training Webinar produced for Q-SORT by [QED](#), with additional support from partner Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light..

In the past few years we have seen a consistent rise in the popularity and value of webinars as an essential training, communication, and engagement tool.

The video of the webinar also offers a unique opportunity for engagement. The project will continue to promote on-demand webinars so that their audiences will get larger and more engaged, and spend more time watching webinars, both live and on-demand. In planning the next webinars we will evaluate the effectiveness of the previous ones and use this information as a guideline to help the Q-SORT consortium create, promote, and deliver even more successful webinars.

ANNEX 1: DESIGN AND POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS OF PATTERNED ELECTRON MIRRORS

Design and potential applications of patterned electron mirrors

Pieter Kruit, Maurice Krielaart, Yuri van Staaden and Sergey Loginov

*Delft University of Technology, Department of Imaging Physics,
Delft, The Netherlands*

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Google Images “electron microscopy protein structure”

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Cryo electron microscopy

CRYO-ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

A beam of electron is fired at a frozen protein solution. The emerging scattered electrons pass through a lens to create a magnified image on the detector, from which their structure can be worked out.

Callaway (2015) Nature 525 p.172

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Noisy images

MICROSCOPY

Microscopy 62(1): 43–50 (2013)
 doi: 10.1093/jmicro/dfs004

Review

Problems in obtaining perfect images by single-particle electron cryomicroscopy of biological structures in amorphous ice

Richard Henderson* and Greg McMullan

Fig. 1. (a) Experimental and (b) simulated single-particle images of apoferritin, a 450 kDa particle that has the shape of a hollow sphere with 432 symmetry and an outside diameter of 130 Å. The experimental images were recorded on an FEI Polara G2 microscope at 300 keV using an FEI Falcon II detector with exposures of 16 e/Å². The simulated images were calculated as described in the text, to produce

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Image formation

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Radiation damage limits the allowable dose

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Radiation damage limits the allowable dose

Dose rate comparable to radiation level at 30 meters of nuclear explosion of a 10 ton H-bomb

The big question: can we do something to reduce the dose and still get the information?

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Transmission electron microscope

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Electron source

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Magnetic lens

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Electrostatic lens

Light optics

electron optics

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Electron mirror

Light optics

electron optics

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Semi transparent mirror

Light optics

electron optics

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Elitzur-Vaidman bomb tester

Thought experiment: detect a sensitive bomb that explodes if hit by a single photon.

A click at detector 2 reveals the presence of the bomb without any interaction between the photon and the bomb having taken place.

But: low efficiency, 2/3 chance of the bomb exploding.

Elitzur and Vaidman, Found. Phys. **23**, 987 (1993)

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Efficient Elitzur-Vaidman bomb tester

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What if we had a semitransparent electron mirror?

PHYSICAL REVIEW A 80, 040902(R) (2009)

Noninvasive electron microscopy with interaction-free quantum measurements

William P. Putnam and Mehmet Fatih Yanik*

*Department of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science and Research Laboratory of Electronics,
 Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, USA*

(Received 20 January 2009; published 23 October 2009)

ULTRAMICROSCOPY 164 (2016) 31-45

Designs for a quantum electron microscope

P.Kruit, R.G.Hobbs, C.S.Kim, Y.Yang, V.R.Manfrinato, J.Hammer, S.Thomas, P.Weber, B.Klopper,
 C.Kohstall, T.Juffmann, M.A.Kasevich, P.Hommelhoff, K.K.Berggren

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Spatial light modulators

Many spatial light modulators (SLMs) are high-resolution liquid crystal panels with micron-sized individually addressable pixels.

Light optics

electron optics

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SLM applications

www.i-med.ac.at/dpmp/bmp/research/slm/

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 INNSBRUCK

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Design and potential applications of patterned electron mirrors

Pieter Kruit, Maurice Krielaart, Yuri van Staaden and Sergey Loginov

*Delft University of Technology, Department of Imaging Physics,
Delft, The Netherlands*

Examples of transmission wave front manipulation

Boersch phase plate (contrast enhancement)
E. Majorovits et al, Ultram. 107, 213-226 (2007)

Sculpted thin films (aberration correction)
R. Shiloh et al, Ultram. 189 46-53 (2018)

Holographic reconstruction (vortex beams)
J. Verbeeck et al, Nature lett. 467, 301-304 (2010)

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A voltage-patterned mirror for electrons

$$d\theta = 2\pi \frac{dz}{\lambda(z)} \quad \text{with } \lambda = \frac{h}{\sqrt{2meU(z)}}$$

The local phase in the reflected wave front depends on the depth of the reflection point.

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Reflection of plane wave

PHYSICAL REVIEW A 98, 063806 (2018)
Grating mirror for diffraction of electrons
 M.A.R. Krielaart and P. Kruit

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A topography-patterned mirror for electrons

$$d\vartheta = 2\pi \frac{dz}{\lambda(z)} \quad \text{with } \lambda = \frac{h}{\sqrt{2meU(z)}}$$

$$U(x, z) = E_z \cdot z - E_z \cdot A_z \cdot e^{-\frac{2\pi z}{a}} \cdot \cos\left(2\pi \frac{x}{a}\right)$$

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WKB approximation

At 10 kV/mm, 1 V difference means 100 nm deeper into the field

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A line pattern (grating) gives diffraction

Intensity in diffracted beams depends on spatial frequency

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Spatial light modulators

Light optics

electron optics

Many spatial light modulators (SLMs) are high-resolution liquid crystal panels with micron-sized individually addressable pixels.

Semi transparent mirror

Light optics

electron optics

X %

100 %

(100-X) %

A Spatial Electron Modulator can be used as a semitransparent mirror!

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How to separate reflected from incoming beam?

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How to separate reflected from incoming beam?

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Double mirror configuration

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A 'virtual' phase plate

Generic phase manipulation

- Topological patterning
- Voltage patterning

Positioning at a cross-over in the column

- Patterned electron mirrors
- Electrostatic deflectors

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A test system under development

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To be tested in an SEM specimen chamber

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Application: Interaction-lean imaging

Elitzur-Vaidman bomb tester

Thought experiment: detect a sensitive bomb that explodes if hit by a single photon.

A click at detector 2 reveals the presence of the bomb without any interaction between the photon and the bomb having taken place.
But: low efficiency, 2/3 chance of the bomb exploding.

Elitzur and Vaidman, *Found. Phys.* **23**, 987 (1993)

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Efficient Elitzur-Vaidman bomb tester

white pixel

black pixel

Reference beam
 Inelastic beam
 Sample beam

Mach-Zehnder Interferometer for electrons

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QEM model for image simulations

QEM model for two-beam coupling and reference beam in vacuum

Entering the coupler are the reference beam with amplitude $R(n-1)$ and the sample beam with amplitude $S(n-1)$. The coupler couples a part ρ of the reference beam into the sample beam and vice versa:

$$R(n) = \sqrt{\rho} \cdot R(n-1) + e^{i\pi/2} \sqrt{1-\rho} \cdot S(n-1)$$

$$Sc(n) = \sqrt{\rho} \cdot S(n-1) + e^{i\pi/2} \sqrt{1-\rho} \cdot R(n-1)$$

In the sample with transparency α , the sample beam loses amplitude and changes phase by ϕ_s . On its way through the microscope we can also add an arbitrary phase ϕ_r .

$$S(n) = e^{i(\phi_s + \phi_r)} \sqrt{\alpha} \cdot Sc(n)$$

The signal that gets lost is

$$I(n) = (1 - \alpha) \cdot Sc(n)^* \cdot Sc(n)$$

When we run these in a loop, we can keep track of the dose passing through the sample and the total dose that gets lost.

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Image simulation in matlab

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Possible samples in simulation

(a) (b) (c)

(d) (e)

MARV VP35 HIV-1 Gag protein

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Proteins in simulation from protein data bank

Figure 2.6: (a) Shows the relative spatial location of the MARV VP35 protein. (b) Shows the latter for the HIV-1 Gag protein. (c) Shows a histogram of the constituent atoms in the MARV VP35 protein. (d) Shows the latter for the HIV-1 Gag protein.

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Projected potentials and phase shifts at 300keV

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Black sample amplitude contrast

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Grey levels, amplitude contrast

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QEM amplitude contrast

Conclusions so far:

1. QEM could increase the dose limited resolution in silhouette imaging from a typical 1nm in regular dark field imaging to 0.1 nm for 100 roundtrips in the resonator.
2. "Black" may be interpreted as a transparency = 0 to about 0.9, but more transparent samples need many more roundtrips.

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QEM phase contrast simulations

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QEM model for image simulations

QEM model for two-beam coupling and reference beam in vacuum

Entering the coupler are the reference beam with amplitude $R(n-1)$ and the sample beam with amplitude $S(n-1)$. The coupler couples a part ρ of the reference beam into the sample beam and vice versa:

$$R(n) = \sqrt{\rho} \cdot R(n-1) + e^{i\pi/2} \sqrt{1-\rho} \cdot S(n-1)$$

$$S(n) = \sqrt{\rho} \cdot S(n-1) + e^{i\pi/2} \sqrt{1-\rho} \cdot R(n-1)$$

In the sample with transparency α , the sample beam loses amplitude and changes phase by φ_s . On its way through the microscope we can also add an arbitrary phase φ_r .

$$S(n) = e^{i(\varphi_s + \varphi_r)} \sqrt{\alpha} \cdot S(n)$$

The signal that gets lost is

$$I(n) = (1 - \alpha) \cdot S(n)^* \cdot S(n)$$

When we run these in a loop, we can keep track of the dose passing through the sample and the total dose that gets lost.

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QEM phase contrast

The effects of phase shift
 Blue = Reference beam
 Red = Sample beam

FIG. 10. (Color online) Results for an IFM process of a fully transparent sample as a function of the phase shift ϕ induced by the sample for $N = 2$ (a), $N = 5$ (b), and $N = 50$ (c). Shown here are P_R (dotted blue line) and P_S (dashed red line).

Sebastian Thomas,^{1,2,4} Christoph Kohstall,³ Pieter Kruit,⁴ and Peter Hommelhoff^{1,2}
 PHYSICAL REVIEW A **90**, 053840 (2014)

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QEM phase contrast simulations

Dose [e/nm²] 43800
 Phase shift: 0.8π

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QEM phase contrast with transparency 0.5

Dose [e/nm ²]	4274	4294	6249	12145	33115
Losses [e/nm ²]	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000

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Phase contrast curves

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QEM phase contrast

Figure 3.13: Simulated R-, S- and L detection results of the QEM, for successively higher m , whilst imaging two HIV-1 Gag protein orientations in 20 nm of vitreous ice using 300keV electrons. As m increases, the detection intensities are increasingly restricted to that which negates an additionally applied phase shift, of -0.017π . The SNR decreases at large m as significant transitions amongst the detection probabilities occur at increasingly large transparency and thus eventually beyond our uniform transparency of 0.9416. Loss is approximately 6100 e/nm^2 for all simulations. The dose is 224256, 12714, 16404, 50864 and 99721 e/nm^2 for the successive simulations. For a more complete set of the simulation specifications, the reader is referred to Appendix B.

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Iso-phase lines for very large m

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Resolution using Iso-phase lines

Phase resolution versus N for alpha = 0,99; 0,95; 0,9; 0,8

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Notice phase contrast in STEM !

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A voltage-patterned mirror for electrons

$$d\theta = 2\pi \frac{dz}{\lambda(z)} \text{ with } \lambda = \frac{h}{\sqrt{2meU(z)}}$$

The local phase in the reflected wave front depends on the depth of the reflection point.

QEM phase contrast with transparency 0.5

Dose [e/nm ²]	4274	4294	6249	12145	33115
Losses [e/nm ²]	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000

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Double mirror configuration

Iso-phase lines for very large m

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Design and potential applications of patterned electron mirrors

Pieter Kruit, Maurice Krielaart, Yuri van Staaden and Sergey Loginov

*Delft University of Technology, Department of Imaging Physics,
Delft, The Netherlands*

Potentials and expectations, theories and designs.... But no images or data !

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ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL